

Skills 4 eosc

Milestone Report 7.5 Sustainability Analysis

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Abstract

This milestone report outlines the methodology and conclusions of the analysis of sustainability of outputs generated by the Project. The Business Model Canvas analysis adapted for Value Networks has been used to analyse the sustainability, defining clear criteria for the short-term sustainable evolution. The Competence Centre Network is seen as a main vehicle to take the community and outcomes of Skills4EOSC beyond the duration of the project funding. The report outlines gaps, risks, and envisioned steps to ensure the short-term sustainability of project outputs

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within the scope of the Competence Centre Network, as well as initial discussion on the long-term viability.

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

<i>Terminology/Acronym</i>	<i>Definition</i>
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
BMC	Business Model Canvas

CCNet	Competence Centre Network
OS	Open Science
FTE	Full-time equivalent
PM	Person-month
LMS	Learning Management System
AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
OA5	Opportunity Area 5

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1 Executive summary

According to the definition in the [Encyclopedia Britannica](#), "Sustainability [is] the long-term viability of a community, set of social institutions, or societal practice." While most of definitions and further explanations do tend to address the environmental aspect of sustainability, we will be focusing on this particular definition in the project.

We will consider that the outputs of the project are sustainable after the end of the project if:

- it has an owner who is able and willing to maintain, evolve, and eventually phase-out the particular output;
- there are procedures set out for the evolution;
- the necessary resources are there to ensure the continuous availability.

It is clear that we are looking into two horizons of sustainability: short-term and long-term. Short-term sustainability is measured in months after the end of the project. The requirement for the short-term sustainability is to ensure the availability of all of the outputs of the project as well as ensuring the work of communities associated with the project (see chapter 3 on more in-depth analysis), and kick-off of processes of evolution of outputs. Long-term sustainability aims at ensuring long-term activities of the community associated with the project outcomes, ensuring their evolution and phase-out if necessary. The value proposition, will have to undergo the evolution adapting to the constantly changing needs of the research and education community. In this analysis we will refrain from assumptions of how the outputs of the project are going to evolve in the long term. We would concentrate on the sustainability of the community environment that allows this evolution.

The analysis of sustainability focuses on the loose application of the Business Model canvas. Chapter 2 overviews the methodology. Chapter 3 outlines the identified gaps for the short term, as well as challenges for the long-term sustainability. The report concludes with the Chapter 4 outlining the potential main actions required before the end of the project to address these gaps.

MS 7.5 Report – Analysis of Sustainability

The analysis made so far, sees the Competence Centre Network as a main vehicle to ensure the sustainability of the project outcomes, with the potential to house the network activities within the established organisation like EOSC Association.

2 Methodology

The team working on sustainability has identified three main groups of outcomes of the Skills4EOSC project that contribute to the sustained impact of the project:

1. Skills4EOSC Competence Centre Network, Knowledge dissemination, Advocacy, Monitoring, and Network expansion;
2. Training, upskilling, quality assurance, and community standards;
3. User Support Network and other professional networks.

The task has decided to use business model canvas (BMC) [BMC] to analyse the sustainability aspect of identified groups of outputs. BMC allows to identify the key users, values, actions (services) as well as required resources, costs and potential revenue streams. Criteria of the BMC analysis were considered for each group.

Figure 1 Business model canvas, source [BMC]

The analysis also will use the adaptation of the BMC model to “value networks” specifics where appropriate [VALUE].

A business model canvas typically has 10 areas of analysis, with the descriptions adapted to reflect the particularity of Competence Centre Network:

1. **Customer Segments or Key Users** – Most important customers (e.g., teachers, students); Instead of just defining customers, this element should expand to include key stakeholders in the network (e.g., participants, collaborators, funders, institutions). For the project outputs, each will have a slightly different customer segment.
2. **Customer Relationships** – The original BMC model suggests to envision the relationship each customer segment expects: e.g., customer acquisition, retention and upselling. However, for the outputs of the project and overall Competence Centre Network following this approach to the letter does not reflect the reality. Instead of focusing on customer acquisition and retention, this element highlights the relationship dynamics within the network in the analysis. This involves managing collaboration, trust-building, and knowledge-sharing practices. The relationship is interactive and collaborative, fostering co-creation and mutual support.
3. **Channels** – How the value proposition is delivered. Will it be online publicly available, through the members of networks? Competence Centres are the channel to deliver the outputs of the project and the value of the network. This section therefore expands from traditional delivery channels to collaborative tools and platforms that enable communication and interaction across the network. Channels are no longer just about delivering value to customers but ensuring that the entire value network has the means to exchange knowledge, resources, and feedback efficiently through shared repositories, communication platforms, and meetings.
4. **Value Proposition** – Value creation for customers and stakeholders: e.g., a standard level of education for a specific profile. This is a summary of what the activities (project outputs) will deliver, may form a different component of the overall value for different segments of stakeholders, e.g. teachers, funders, policy-makers. In a value network, the Value Proposition also shifts from focusing solely on individual customers, because network participants form a significant segment of stakeholders. Therefore, to assess the value

proposition of the network, one needs to consider the shared value created for all participants. This includes how each actor in the network benefits, learns, or grows from the interaction, shared knowledge, collaboration opportunities, or access to resources.

5. **Key Activities (services, products)** – These are all the activities needed to realize and maintain the value proposition, and to power everything else involved in keeping the outputs of the project alive and evolving. Key activities would be framed in terms of collective actions within the network. These are the shared tasks that contribute to the network’s objectives and long-term goals, like joint research, co-development of tools, or shared advocacy. It’s about understanding that these activities are not done in isolation but require collective efforts across different network participants.
6. **Key Partnerships** – The people who will help you fulfil the key activities, using the key resources. Value Network Participants in a value network, key partners extend beyond traditional suppliers or collaborators. Partners are integral members of a network, co-creating value through shared expertise, resources, and collaboration. The Key Partnerships section of the BMC would be adapted to focus on the entire ecosystem of stakeholders, ensuring that all players, from contributors to end users, are considered.
7. **Key Resources** – The tools needed to get key actions implemented, stretching across all areas the canvas covers, for example, customer retention. Resources in the Competence Centre Network are usually shared or co-owned by the network participants. The discussion on Key Resources shifts to include collective assets such as contributions of human resources (time), data, shared infrastructure, and expertise. The resources needed for the network’s success are distributed, and members contribute what they can to sustain the system.
8. **Cost Structure** – The Cost Structure of the Competence Centre Network is adapted to emphasize shared costs and joint investments in maintaining the network. Members contribute based on their participation and the value they gain. In-kind contributions form the basis of the network with potential for the joint funding, or shared infrastructure costs.

9. **Revenue Streams** – Where you find potential revenue sources (e.g., in-kind contributions, membership fees). The analysis provides discussion based on the accumulated inputs and expert opinions of the task experts.
10. **Sustainability** – Sustainability here is not only about environmental or financial stability. It focuses on the short-term sustainability and long-term health of the network, ensuring that it remains adaptive, inclusive, and capable of evolving over time. This includes managing stakeholder engagement, fostering continuous collaboration, and supporting shared values.

The sustainability part is discussed in the subsequent chapters in this document as well as in the deliverable 7.4.

The BMC analysis allows to identify key gaps and requirements for action when compared to the existing situation.

3 Component Evaluation – gaps to sustainability

The analysis of gaps is impossible without some context, that summarises the value of the Competence Centre Network. The value proposition of the CCNet has been outlined in the Berlin workshop [BERLIN]. It reflects the value primary for the Competence Centres; however, the considerations are wider:

- Competence Centre Network is valuable as a community forum to:
 - Discuss best practices
 - Agree on the community standards (lightweight)
 - Use case: Scientists should obtain standard knowledge on OS/EOSC regardless of their scientific domain.
 - Inclusive approach
 - Pan-European level of interaction
 - E.g., Norway Competence centres rather a different kind of value in European level than in national level network activities.
- The competences addressed by the Competence Centres (and consequently, by the Network) are wider than Skills4EOSC and EOSC – more open science competences.
- Network allows flexibility, its membership is not necessarily rigidly national distribution, therefore it is perceived as a bottom-up initiative.
- Concentrate on the value to scientist – to easily find and obtain necessary skills/competences
- Network can help competence centres to be sustainable

We will base the gaps analysis on this value proposition. The differences between the project-based Competence Centre Network and the Network after the end of the project first of all include coverage of costs and general resources, mostly in-kind contribution of time of employees. The project also provides the organisational scaffolding for the Network, while the independent organisational structure will have to be put in place after the end of the project to ensure the continuation of the activity as well as availability and evolution of project results.

3.1 Analysis of costs and resources for participation

This sub-chapter analyses the expected requirement of resources for CCs to participate in and contribute to the Network, including resource allocation, staffing, training, and infrastructure needs. The availability of these resources is necessary to ensure the Network survivability immediately after the end of the project and

3.1.1 In-kind contributions

The participation in the network would require each member to contribute the time of their employees as well as allocate some travel budget to travel to physical meetings. These activities would range depending on the involvement of each member. In order to determine the ranges of potential involvements, we can estimate several levels:

- Minimal involvement would require the attendance of the plenary meetings (once a year) as well as meetings of working groups contributing to the content.
- Normal involvement would imply in addition taking part in leading working groups and more active contributions to the outcomes of the efforts.
- Presidential level contribution would mean taking responsibility for the whole network and its outcomes for a period of time.

The actual contribution will likely be different based on the particular partner involved therefore it is not possible to estimate precisely. At the current level of activities of the network we estimate that minimal involvement level would range from 1 to 4 PM per year, medium involvement would range from 3 to 8 PM per year, and presidential involvement would require upwards from 6PM per year (0.5 FTE).

The project team considers that in-kind contributions would be sufficient to ensure the value of the Competence Centre Network and support for continuous support and evolution of outputs of the project in short term, under the condition that all Competence Centres – members of the network contribute to the value and activities of the network.

Figure 2 Estimated levels of participation

3.1.2 Infrastructure and services

In order to ensure the maintenance of the network there are several infrastructure elements required to support it:

1. Mailing-list system to ensure communications with the member as well as communications within the working-groups or other organisational entities established by the network, e.g. Editorial board.
2. Video-conferencing system. There's a number of solutions available for the R&E community e.g. eduMeet and others.
3. Repository of materials. Repositories of scientific publications like zenodo.org can be used, and quite a lot of outputs of the project have been submitted and available through Zenodo. Furthermore, we suggest that all new produced materials to be uploaded under the tag community Skills4EOOSC CC Network (to be added as a new community in Zenodo). Particularly it concerns the publicly available data and publications. Repositories of public data do not resolve the requirement for internal or restricted document repository, however the requirement to have such restricted repository has to be discussed by the CC Network.
4. Learning management system (LMS) to host all the training courses created during the project. LMS must support the courses framework with enrolment as well as certification and assessment framework.

5. Continuation of the recognition framework using trusted certificate authorities to issue necessary credentials to trainees who completed the different training courses.
6. Shared space with tools for collaborative development of new outputs.
7. Website.

All infrastructure has to maintain the integration with eduGAIN AAI federation as it is the standard approach for authentication in the R&E community. The infrastructure and services will require continuous support and maintenance. We estimate that the maintenance of the infrastructure would require approximately 3-4PM per year depending upon the tool-set composition and e.g., use of publicly available platforms like Zenodo or GitHub.

Particular attention has to be paid to the usage of cloud-based shared systems like the ones provided by Google and Microsoft or the ones with the possibility of on-site installation, like OnlyOffice. These systems have to ensure long-term availability as well as security of data and users, especially in the light of current geopolitical situation.

Estimations of the Annual Recurring Costs (ARC) for the outputs of the project are provided in the Table 1. These costs are estimated based on the input from the project coordinator, who operates these systems currently. Some variation may be expected if these components were to be provided by any other entity or the decision is made to use the freely available components such as mailing-list servers. Costs of each component also include their maintenance as well as necessary licence fees.

The presented figures represent the short-term projection only. Long-term cost projections will depend upon the re-evaluation of outputs and their feasibility.

Table 1 Estimated annual costs

<i>No</i>	<i>Infrastructure component or service</i>	<i>ARC</i>
1	Mailing-list system	7 900,00 €
2	Video-conferencing system	15 900,00 €
4	Learning management system	15 600,00 €

6	Shared space for development (and restricted repository)	18 280,00 €
7	Website	13 600,00 €
	Total yearly cost estimation	71 280,00 €

3.2 Long-Term Viability Discussion

In order to be viable long-term, the Competence Centre Network will have to continue delivering and evolving the value proposition towards its members helping Competence Centres to advance their own value. The long-term **Institutional and Organisational viability** is becoming one of the highest priorities. Current short-term roadmap envisions establishment of the light-weight organisation based on the in-kind contribution. The viability of such organisational setup has to be proven and will require re-evaluation e.g. with the election of second presidency. Current documentation leaves quite a number of items to be decided by the network, including e.g. term duration and possibility of consecutive terms of presidency. The difficulty to change the presiding organisation either because of lack of candidates or because of the complexity of the procedure would indicate that the set-up of the whole Network has to be reconsidered.

Another option for the long-term organisational viability would be to **join an existing international organisation** of which the EOSC Association may be an obvious candidate, although at the time of writing of this report the Opportunity Area 5 (OA5) in the ESOA Association does not seem to have sufficient capacity to house the CC Network. Joining the federation of EOSC Nodes may be for consideration. This would allow implementation of measures to ensure long-term financial sustainability in terms of membership fees or funding from external sources.

Evolution of the value proposition is the ultimate condition for the long-term viability of the CC Network and long-term sustainability of the impact of the Skills4EOSC project. The member and stakeholder engagement would be

the ultimate indicator that the Network provides added value and helps to enhance respective value propositions of its members and helps Competence Centres to become better at fulfilling their mission.

Sustainable stakeholder engagement and community building is tightly coupled with the evolution of the value proposition. Current short-term setup allows for the easy expansion of the community of the Competence Centres, simplifying the process of becoming a member to signing of the Letter of Intent. The governance of the Network has to make sure that the procedure facilitates network inclusiveness as well as member contributions, ensuring fairness across the spectrum of participants in the long-term perspective.

Policy and regulatory alignment is one of the conditions necessary to increase the sustainability in the long-term. The EOSC environment is highly dynamic, and EOSC actors are constantly re-evaluating their roles and positions. The current federated setup of EOSC nodes has yet to prove its viability, and the role of the EOSC Association is not perceived as stable within the community. This imposes an uncertainty of what knowledge and practices will be required by the R&E community in the long-term perspective. Competence centres seem to be relatable to the concept of EOSC Nodes, enriching the value of EOSC Nodes from the infrastructure, services, and data into the area of standardised knowledge distribution. This direction has to be reevaluated when more EOSC Nodes join the federation.

3.3 Major risks and potential mitigations

The Table 2 provides risk registry for the Competence Centre Network together with mitigations. Listed mitigations will have to be re-evaluated and eventually undertaken by the CC Network General Assembly after the end of the project in the event of materialisation of risks.

Table 2 Risk register for sustainability

<i>Risk</i>	<i>Risk type</i>	<i>Impact</i>	<i>Mitigation strategies</i>
<i>Technological and infrastructure risks</i>	Short-term	Medium	The use of the publicly available resources. Set-up of post-project resources and services for all outputs, well before the

			end. Identifying the missing parts and actively looking for solutions.
<i>Not sufficient engagement from members</i>	Short-term	Severe	Ensure that the outputs provide value corresponding with required engagement. Evaluate which outputs to continue. Engage wider community. Widespread advocacy work for the project outputs. Look for additional funding opportunities.
<i>Collision with other communities</i>	Long-term	Medium	Coordinate and engage with similar efforts within known European and national landscape
<i>Work programme of the CC Network not sufficiently identified (in terms of reflections and actions to be taken).</i>	Long-term	Medium	Look for additional funding opportunities. Ensure that working groups are healthy and delivering value to the community.
<i>Too diverse community (too many different competence centres joining the network)</i>	Long-term	Medium	Revisit the organisational structure, admission of new members. Current organisational structure has been proposed taking into account relatively low number of the Competence Centres.
<i>Knowledge transfer</i>	Long-term	Medium	Ensure that the knowledge and expertise generated within the network are successfully shared and adopted by relevant stakeholders.
<i>Governance and coordination risks</i>	Short-term	Severe	Establish a well-defined governance model with clear roles, responsibilities and decision-making processes for all partners involved in the CC Network. Strong leadership and coordination. Regular communication and reporting.
<i>Alignment with EOSC objectives</i>	Long-term	Medium	Ensure that the activities and outcomes of CCN align closely with the evolving goals of EOSC.

4 Conclusions and actions

The Competence Centre Network is seen as a main vehicle to ensure the sustainability of the impact of Skills4EOOSC project. The constant interaction with Competence Centres has provided clear indication that organisations are willing and able to engage in the networking activities. Competence centres see the value in the Network, it would be advantageous to use the momentum and enthusiasm to ensure the sustained impact and own life of project results beyond the duration of the project.

A number of actions have to be undertaken before the end of the project to ensure that the Competence Centre Network is organised and capable of operation independently from the project. These actions can be loosely grouped into organisational actions and technical actions. This chapter provides the outline and discussion of both directions, as well as discussion on the potential funding options (revenue streams).

4.1 Organisational options and actions

The Berlin workshop with the Competence Centres clearly indicated that members of the Network do not see the network as a separate organisation with its own budget, office, etc. It means that the Network has to be organised as an informal community effort. The role of the Competence Centre Network requires an adoption of a lightweight structure and decision making even if the Network does not establish itself as an independent organisation.

Initial organisation structure of the CC Network has been proposed in the initial version of the Deliverable D7.3, and is due to be updated after the issue of this report. The updated structure and description of the CC Network will reflect the situation at the current state of the project implementation and will outline the lightweight organisation structure.

Figure 3 Proposed simplified governance structure of the CC Network

The organisational steps required order to start operation of the Network after the end of the project are outlined below:

1. The Organisation structure of the Network has to be documented, and adopted by the competence centres. Since there’s no formal membership and no formal organisation, the adoption and adherence of the Competence Centres to the agreed practices will be essential to successful sustainability of the outputs of the project. Organisation structure also has to define the way of new members accepted to the network, as well as suspension or expulsion of members if necessary.
2. The first formal meeting of the General Assembly has to be held, where the first Presidency has to be appointed, as well as Editorial board, and working groups necessary to sustain the project results, e.g. User Support Network working group.
3. The elements and solutions for the infrastructure and services have to be agreed-upon.

There may be several alternatives of synergies with existing efforts. Most notably, the Opportunity Area 5 “Skills, Training, Rewards, Recognition & Upscaling” [OA5] has some shared goals. It is however unclear at the time of writing of the report how the Competence Centre Network would be sharing

the organisation structure with the OA5 group, as the future of the opportunity area is not clear within the programme of the EOSC Association. The Association would be a desired organisation to house the Competence Centre Network. It would provide the value of a formal office, and a more solid basis for sustainability of the outputs of the project.

There are other efforts based on the Competence Centres, most notably from the OSCARS project (<https://oscars-project.eu/>), where thematic competence centres are being established. It is bound by the same time-limited funding as Skills4EOSC and would face the similar sustainability issues with the end of the project. Working Competence Centre Network would provide a vehicle to accommodate also the outputs of other projects like OSCARS.

The Competence Centre Network (CC Network) of Skills4EOSC can establish a strong and sustainable collaboration with the emerging European and national **EOSC Nodes** by leveraging its expertise in training, capacity building, and Open Science services. A key element of this relationship is the EOSC European Node’s **training catalogue**, which will serve as a central service and should be interoperable with the training catalogues of national EOSC Nodes. The CC Network can support this effort by aligning training resources, methodologies, and standards across different communities, ensuring a harmonized and accessible training ecosystem.

Additionally, by sharing expertise, co-developing materials, and contributing to knowledge transfer, the CC Network can help strengthen national Nodes, enabling them to provide high-quality, context-specific training while remaining connected to the broader European landscape. Through coordinated service portfolios, and a shared vision for Open Science skills development, the CC Network and EOSC Nodes can create a sustainable framework that fosters long-term engagement, innovation, and capacity building across Europe.

4.2 Financial options (revenue streams)

The sustainability of outputs of the Skills4EOSC project will require contributions from the members of the Competence Centre Network, both in time of their staff, as well as some infrastructure solutions and services.

The Competence Centres indicated that the in-kind contribution to the operations of the Network as well as sustainability of the outputs are possible if no external funding can be attracted. It leaves therefore only two options to achieve financial sustainability:

- **In-kind contribution by members.** This option means that all the components, activities, infrastructure, and services of the Competence Centre Network would rely on membership to engage with adequate resources to sustain the effort. It would also serve as the ultimate means to ensure that the Network and outputs of the project present the value to members. The particular responsibility in this model would befall on the institution of presidency of the network. The competence centre elected/appointed as a first president of the network, will have to contribute significant effort to keep the Network operational through the critical time after the end of the project. This is the most likely scenario for the short-term future immediately after the end of the project.
- **External funding sources.** The task 8.3 of the project has outlined approximately 100 potential options for external funding, including national and regional funding options as well as more than 80 initiatives without funding. External funding could be used to compensate the necessary efforts and infrastructure at least partially, especially in case of presidency or other larger involvement of Competence Centres. Figure 4 and Figure 5 provide outline of funding options. It is clear that most of the recorded instruments are at the national level, and would therefore benefit a limited number of Competence Centres. At the time of writing, no known applications have been approved, therefore it is not likely that the external funding will be available immediately after the end of the project.

Figure 4 Number of funding instruments by level as registered by task 8.3

Figure 5 Number of funding instruments by country as registered by task 8.3

4.3 First steps of the road-map to sustainability

Team of task 7.5 has identified a number of steps necessary to be completed before end of the project to ensure the sustainability of the outputs and

impact. They are summarised in the Table 3 together with their current status at the time of writing of the report. For the project duration all the steps will be undertaken with the guidance of project participants, and WP7 in particular.

Table 3 First steps to ensure the sustainability

No	Description	Responsible	Status
1	Organisation structure of CCNetwork	Tasks 7.2 and 7.5	In progress, Initial proposal was too complicated
2	Adoption of organisation structure	Task 7.2	Pending, has to happen before the first meeting of the General Assembly.
3	First meeting of the CCNetwork General Assembly	Tasks 7.2 and 7.5	Pending, potentially during the final project event
4	Appointment of the first presidency	CC Network General Assembly	Pending, potentially during the final project event
5	Appointment of the editorial board	CC Network General Assembly	In progress, the discussions have started
6	Initial list of working groups	CC Network General Assembly	Pending.
7	Establishing infrastructure components and services	CC Network General Assembly	Pending, initial proposals during the final project event.
8	First independent meeting of CC Network General Assembly Verification of infrastructure resources and services	President of CC Network	Pending, before the end of the project.

Programme of future meetings and works.		
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5 References

<i>No</i>	<i>Description/Link</i>
BMC	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Business_model_canvas
VALUE	https://essay.utwente.nl/63024/1/Thesis_report_Maher_Dara_final.pdf
BERLIN	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1cfsim95-3zzH3kJArfUMbgG9Py4lhdsB_u2xtiRDH2Y
OA5	https://eosc.eu/opportunity-area-exp/oa5-skills-training-rewards-recognition-upscaling/